

Patriotism and global citizenship: The fundamentals for enhancing NSTP curriculum for SDCA

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Abstract – *This study aimed to assess the level of Patriotism and Global Citizenship of selected students of St. Dominic College of Asia. A total of 190 students enrolled in National Service Training Program from different courses participated in the study. This study utilized a self-made test which is a 20-item 5-point Likert scale that will measure Patriotism and Global Citizenship. For Patriotism factor, results showed that across all courses, except for Biology course, the computed mean score is within 4.20-5.00 with a verbal interpretation of Very High Patriotism. For Global Citizenship factor, results showed that across all courses, except for Biology course, the computed mean score is within 4.20-5.00 with a verbal interpretation of Very Global Citizenship. The results of this study will be used as basis in enhancing National Service Training Program Curriculum.*

Keywords: Patriotism, global citizenship, National Service Training Program, St. Dominic College of Asia.

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Introduction

Since 2011, Syria experienced devastation due to the conflict between the government authorities and rebel groups. The saddest part is, it turns out the victims are the civilians. On June 29, 2018, the Human Rights Watch (HRW) the casualties are about 511,000 (excluding the present casualties from July 2018 to present). The situation forced the civilians to migrate abroad specially to Europe, Australia and other Continents. Yet, the nightmare of the Syrians did not cease upon the leaving their own country; as what the Syrian - refugee of Greece described, “Europe does not see us human” (Kakissis, 2018). The same experience portrays of “Rohingya in Myanmar”. From 2016 up to present, experts fear that “437,000 are dead” (Barron, 2018). The situation drove the Rohingya to look for a shelter to other countries. Unfortunately, as reported by Guardian Magazine on August 2019, some Rohingya who evacuated Bangladesh were also maltreated by the citizens of Bangladesh; “They threatened us, saying we should leave or else they’d kill us. Why should we get punished if others did something bad?” (AFP, 2019).

What can be the challenges and opportunities of this phenomenon? This paper provides different ideas when it comes to patriotism and global citizenship in implementing the National Service Training Program (NSTP) curriculum. The concept of citizenship was derived from kinship of a particular group that shares the same culture. However, as the world becomes modernized, the idea of citizenship becomes a complex issue also.

This part includes ideas from different countries which mainly talks about Global Citizenship. The ideas and conclusion that are included will be a great help to familiarize the

present study. According to the study of McKenzie (1993), in a book *Citizenship Education in Canada*, The Department of Multiculturalism and Citizenship promotes literacy, works to remove discrimination and racism, educates the public about their rights and obligations as Canadian citizens, encourages voluntary action, and advocates for human rights to help new Canadians integrate into society.

A statement from the study of Buchanan et al. (2018), in maintaining global citizenship education in schools: *A challenge for Australian educators and schools*, “While nations do need to seek loyalty from their citizens and use their state-funded education systems as a means of doing so, this should not come at the expense of a commitment and loyalty to the planet and its people.” Global cooperation is needed to effectively address key ongoing global challenges such as food security, growing inequality and the North-South split, the future of work, global warming, and climate change (Cann, 2016), as well as the enormous migration flows, refugee crises, transnational terrorism, ongoing wars and conflicts.

Educating students about global issues is a help for students, as Hansen (2011) puts it, to learn about the value of “reflective openness to new people, ideas, values and practices”, to take on a multi-perspectivity (Deardorff, 2011), to increase greater intercultural understanding and sensitivity (Buchanan, 2006), and display genuine concern for people from outside our local and national boundaries. Global citizenship education is still a contested issue, with a variety of conflicting goals reflected in the curriculum options employed (UNESCO, 2014; Marshall, 2011). Because of various national contexts and perspectives, policies and approaches differ from country to country. This is mirrored in the wide range of GCE techniques used in schools in different countries as surveyed by UNESCO (2014), across Europe (Bourn, 2016), and the UK (Mannion et al., 2011; Marshall, 2011; Oxley & Morris, 2013). This includes economic, or technical-economic, cultural, political, global social-justice or rights-based agendas.

Methods

This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative study. Descriptive research is defined as a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. Data is presented in numbers as quantitative approach. The research developed a self-made survey questionnaire that measures patriotism and global citizenship. The survey is a 20-item 5-Point Likert scale. A total of 190 respondents who are students from different courses of St. Dominic College of Asia. The survey questionnaire was transcribed to an online survey via Google Survey form, and it was distributed to students. Data were collected, tallied, and statistically analyzed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Respondents

Course	Frequency	Percentage
Accountancy	31	16
Biology	2	1
Business Administration	2	1
Communication	2	1
Education	2	1
Hospitality Management	21	11
Information Technology	15	8
Medical Technology	9	5
Multimedia Arts	29	15
Nursing	38	20
Pharmacy	17	9
Physical Therapy	5	3
Psychology	17	9
Total	190	100

The table above shows the frequency distribution of respondents. Out of 190 respondents participated in the study, 31 or 16 percent are Accounting students, two (2) or 1 percent are Biology students, two (2) or 1 percent are Business Administration students, two (2) or 1 percent are Communication students, two (2) or 1 percent are Education students, 21 or 11 percent are Hospitality Management students, 15 or 8 percent are Information Technology students, nine (9) or 5 percent are Medical Technology students, 29 or 15 percent are Multimedia Arts students, 38 or 20 percent are Nursing students, 17 or 9 percent are Pharmacy students, five (5) or 3 percent are Physical Therapy students, and 17 or 9 percent are Psychology students. Hence, there are more Nursing students participated as respondents in the study.

Table 2. Mean Score for Patriotism

Course	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Accountancy	4.60	0.33	Very High
Biology	4.05	0.64	High
Business Administration	4.20	0.42	Very High
Communication	4.25	0.21	Very High
Education	4.50	0.14	Very High
Hospitality Management	4.52	0.34	Very High
Information Technology	4.52	0.38	Very High
Medical Technology	4.46	0.38	Very High
Multimedia Arts	4.42	0.29	Very High
Nursing	4.62	0.37	Very High
Pharmacy	4.45	0.37	Very High
Physical Therapy	4.48	0.13	Very High
Psychology	4.41	0.36	Very High
Overall	4.51	0.35	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.79 = Very Low; 1.80-2.59 = Low; 2.60-3.39 = Uncertain; 3.40-4.19 = High; 4.20-5.00 = Very High

The table above shows the mean score for Patriotism. For Accountancy, the mean score is 4.60 with standard deviation of 0.33 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Biology, the mean score is 4.05 with standard deviation of 0.64 and verbal interpretation of “High”. For Business Administration, the mean score is 4.20 with the standard deviation of 0.42 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Communication, the mean score is 4.25 with the standard deviation of 0.21 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Education, the mean score is 4.50 with the standard deviation of 0.14 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Hospitality Management, the mean score is 4.52 with the standard deviation of 0.34 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Information Technology, the mean score is 4.52 with the standard deviation of 0.38 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Medical Technology, the mean score is 4.46 with the standard deviation of 0.38 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Multimedia Arts, the mean score is 4.42 with the standard deviation of 0.29 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Nursing, the mean score is 4.62 with the standard deviation of 0.37 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Pharmacy, the mean score is 4.45 with the standard deviation of 0.37 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Physical Therapy, the mean score is 4.48 with the standard deviation of 0.13 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. Lastly, for Psychology, the mean score is 4.41 with the standard deviation of 0.36 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. With this, the overall mean is 4.51 with the standard deviation of 0.35 which gives the interpretation of “Very High”.

Table 3. Mean Score for Global Citizenship

Course	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Accountancy	4.43	0.40	Very High
Biology	3.85	0.78	High
Business Administration	4.25	0.49	Very High
Communication	4.55	0.07	Very High
Education	4.40	0.00	Very High
Hospitality Management	4.54	0.38	Very High
Information Technology	4.35	0.49	Very High
Medical Technology	4.32	0.37	Very High
Multimedia Arts	4.32	0.36	Very High
Nursing	4.51	0.39	Very High
Pharmacy	4.44	0.33	Very High
Physical Therapy	4.34	0.38	Very High
Psychology	4.35	0.44	Very High
Overall	4.41	0.39	Very High

Legend: 1.00-1.79 = Very Low; 1.80-2.59 = Low; 2.60-3.39 = Uncertain; 3.40-4.19 = High; 4.20-5.00 = Very High

The table above shows the mean score for Global Citizenship. For Accountancy, the mean score is 4.43 with standard deviation of 0.40 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Biology, the mean score is 3.85 with standard deviation of 0.78 and verbal interpretation of “High”. For Business Administration, the mean score is 4.25 with the standard deviation of 0.49 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Communication, the mean score is 4.55 with the standard deviation of 0.07 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Education, the mean score is 4.40 with the standard deviation of 0.00 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Hospitality Management, the mean score is 4.54 with the standard deviation of 0.38 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Information Technology, the mean score is 4.35 with the standard deviation of 0.49 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Medical Technology, the mean score is 4.32 with the standard deviation of 0.37 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Multimedia Arts, the mean score is 4.32 with the standard deviation of 0.36 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Nursing, the mean score is 4.51 with the standard deviation of 0.39 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Pharmacy, the mean score is 4.44 with the standard deviation of 0.33 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. For Physical Therapy, the mean score is 4.34 with the standard deviation of 0.38 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. Lastly, for Psychology, the mean score is 4.35 with the standard deviation of 0.44 and verbal interpretation of “Very High”. With this, the overall mean is 4.41 with the standard deviation of 0.39 which gives the interpretation of “Very High”.

Discussion

According to the theory of Immanuel Kant that this paper has adapted, ‘Good education itself the source of all that is good in the world’. Educational planning must therefore follow a ‘cosmopolitan’ spirit with commitment to all that is ‘best in the world’. With this, NSTP in the Philippines is a best foundation wherein global citizenship must be connected since patriotism is

present there already. As an individual, as a citizen, ones thinking, and perspective must be in a wider scale to fit in this changing world. This would happen if it started in the way how students are being educated.

As the world grows, it becomes more connected yet it is prone to be more divided so the foundation of education must be reviewed and modified depending on how each individual responds. The first step towards embracing global citizenship in the Philippines is changing the education pattern – adapting the concept of K-12 education. With this, they could easily fit in the wider world. There may be a present curriculum in NSTP but this paper aims to have a change for the reason that the world is also changing. The idea of global citizenship must be included, deepened, and inculcated to everyone and NSTP is the best foundation rather than creating new path navigating the concept of the abovementioned term.

Every individual must be fully aware what is patriotism and how this would lead to a wider term of reference – the Global Citizenship. It is known to us that first-hand experience is the basis of what is the reality, yet, a person must still learn its concept so that in terms of application, there would be a basis. As the world grows, it becomes more connected, yet it is prone to be more divided. As we synthesize, the commitment of everyone must be of the best for the world, therefore the foundation must be strengthened or otherwise modified.

References

- Agence France-Presse. (2019, August 25). *Rohingya refugees shot dead by Bangladesh police during gunfight*. The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/aug/25/rohingya-refugees-shot-dead-by-bangladesh-police-during-gunfight>
- Barron, L. (2018, March 7). *More than 43,000 Rohingya parents may be missing. Experts fear they are dead*. Time. <https://time.com/5187292/rohingya-crisis-missing-parents-refugees-bangladesh/>
- BBC. (2019, October 16). *What's happening in Syria?* CBBC Newsround. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsround/16979186>
- Bourn, D. (2016). Global learning and the school curriculum. *Management in Education*, 30(3), 121-125. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0892020616653178>
- Buchanan, A. (2006). Institutionalizing the just war. *Philosophy & Public Affairs*, 34(1), 2-38. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1088-4963.2006.00051.x>
- Buchanan, J., Burrige, N., & Chodkiewicz, A. (2018). Maintaining global citizenship education in schools: A challenge for Australian educators and schools. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 51–67. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n4.4>
- Cann, O. (2016, January 14). *What are the top global risks for 2016?* World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/what-are-the-top-global-risks-for-2016/>
- Deardorff, J. K. (2011). Assessing intercultural competence. *New Directions for Institutional Research*, 2011(149), 65-79. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ir.381>
- Hansen, D. (2011). *The teacher and the world: A study of cosmopolitanism as education*. Routledge.
- Human Rights Watch. (2019, January 23). World report 2019: Syria. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2019/country-chapters/syria>

- Human Rights Watch. (2019, January 17). World report 2019: Myanmar. <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2019/country-chapters/myanmar-burma>
- Kakassis, J. (2018, March 9). 'Europe does not see us as human': Stranded refugees struggle in Greece. <https://www.npr.org/sections/parallels/2018/03/09/589973165/europe-does-not-see-us-as-human-stranded-refugees-struggle-in-greece>
- Kaulem, D., Banchoff, T., Trolio, S. D., Esteves, P. R., Okabe, M., Pereira, S., & Tolosa, B. (2018). *Task force on civic and political leadership formation* [Position statement]. <https://www.ignited.global/sites/default/files/Civic%20and%20Political%20Leadership.pdf>
- Mannion, G., Biesta, G., Priestley, M., & Ross, H. (2011). The global dimension in education and education for global citizenship: Genealogy and critique. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 9(3-4), 443-456. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2011.605327>
- Marshall, H. (2011). Instrumentalism, ideals and imaginaries: Theorising the contested space of global citizenship education in schools. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 9(3-4), 411-426. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2011.605325>
- McKenzie, H. B. (1993). *Citizenship education in Canada*. Library of Parliament, Research Branch.
- Oxley, L., & Morris, P. (2013). Global citizenship: A typology for distinguishing its multiple conceptions. *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 61(3), 301-325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071005.2013.798393>
- Peterson, A., Milligan, A., & Wood, B. E. (2018). Global citizenship education in Australasia. In I. Davies, L. Ho, D. Kiwan, C. L. Peck, A. Peterson, E. Sant, & Y. Waghid (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of global citizenship and education* (pp. 3-20). https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-59733-5_1
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. (2014). *Teaching and learning: Achieving quality for all*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000225660>